

METHODS OF CORRECT READING.

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Annotation: This article discusses the methods of literary reading of foreign language learners. Methods of correct reading, presentation of reading, expressive reading, literary reading skills.

Keywords: language, thought, method, education, oral speech, reading, competence, speech culture, technology and conscious reading.

Introduction: As society develops, oral speech will develop over time. This Also the literature has evolved in this way. Language is one of the ways of communication between people. With the help of language, Isona express their thoughts to each other and exchange ideas. If we look at history, then there is no tribe that has no sound of their own language. Scientists are learning about the origin of the languages and the similarities of each language for a long time. The place and role of literature in the development of human society is great. Since literature has a stable and constantly repeating character, theory of literature defines the principles and methodology, methods and currents, a literary process based on these general laws that govern the development of literature. Fiction is one of other forms of art, such as; It differs from music, architecture, dance, painting, sculpture. Literature is different from other forms of art such as music, architecture dancing painting and sculpture.

Methods: The unity of writers is reflected in the field of literature. Literature is a historical phenomenon that occurs in a certain period or other period in national literature and is lost in a certain period. The methodology of teaching literature has led to the development of the science of methodology, in particular, the methodology of teaching linguistics as a real science. Literary style occurs when group of writers' creative principles and the historical background are taken as a basis and interpreting the main issues of period that is in solving the idea of ideal heroism In this sense, the concept of style is combined with the concept of a literary school, a literary way.. The main important issues of language teaching are the methods of forming students' literacy, the culture of speech, to one degree or another, expressed a number of methodological and didactic ideas. It is clear that in the methodological literature the problem of students' growing speech has become the object of discussion, such as "speech growth", "speech culture", "speech technique". In accordance with this term, general issues of language teaching are issues such as observation and study of linguistic events, the ability of students to express their views in writing and verbally. The lively, expressive, interesting, juicy and significant speech of the teacher has a positive effect on the formation of students' speech. Therefore, the teacher's speech should be an example for students. Correct and expressive speech is one of the most pressing problems in the education system, which is still a matter of life of any educated person.. Each language teacher must develop various methodological forms and methods of speech of students, which should show all the kidneys of living speech. Thus, a number of methodologists O. Madayev, V.V. Golubkov, A. Khodzhaev in the methodological guidelines for teaching language, language and literature

for the development of oral and written speech of students, much attention is paid to these issues. Key questions of the teaching methodology.

Result.

During the training, the wealth of students' vocabulary increases, and their knowledge expands. Key questions of the teaching methodology. They slowly learn to feel their native language. It is known that the level of study of students is not the same. Some students read this quickly, ignoring the content of the work, while others read it slowly with interest in the content of the work. When teaching linguistic literature, the following issues are considered:

- 1. Growing skills of teaching students;
- 2. Expanding the worldview of students;
- 3. Increasing the mental maturity of students, spiritual beauty, physical maturity;
- 4. Help students have a polite, moral, aesthetic taste;
- 5. Improving oral and written speech skills of students;

Get acquainted with their native language and literature and instill in them a feeling of love. The teacher must solve such problems with excellent methodological skills, complying the rules of education and training. Each lesson must have a specific purpose. When a teacher prepares for a lesson, he chooses working methods depending on the purpose of the topic under study; During the lesson, it is necessary to determine what new knowledge will be provided, what independent work will be done on this topic, what will be done on the development of speech, as well as expressive reading, planning and practice. A specific topic is usually taught in each lesson. The topic of the lesson should be carefully thought out. Preparing students for the lesson (introductory interviews, teacher history, photographs, etc.) should help them become interested in this topic and help them better understand the topic.

Discussion.

Then the student will master the knowledge and skills necessary in the program. Independent work of students should be taken into account in the field of language teaching. Let them be able to give independent views on the works they read, their content and images: in order to be able to do the work on their own, for example, a plan for dividing work into parts. The more expressive and impressive the text, the easier it will be to attract attention to students. When you read the text, the vocabulary of students increases, and the level of thinking expands. You must be conscious. Only then can you get the right and quick reading skills. Develop student learning skills.

When learning, it is important to pay attention to the fact that the reading speed, reading correctly, conscious reading, the ability to read aloud and reading skills. Students' learning proficiency has a primary concern in teaching literature. Read without discarding it, changing the sound, without "swallowing" the last syllable of words. Applying the word emphasis, following the rules of orthoepy (words in Russian): reading speed. Reading speed should be increased in combination with awareness, accuracy and expressiveness. Reading speed is achieved only as a result of exercise. To help students with poor reading speed, you can organize the text in roles.

Conclusions: Conscious reading is the reading of each word and sentence, in contrast to the main ideas in the text. There are words in our language that have several meanings, and these meanings are known in context. For example, do not take these seedlings. The first apple word in the word apple plant is the command verb, and the second is the horse. In conscious

reading, it is necessary to pay close attention to words and suffixes, which mean pampering, contraction and strengthening of the text. Must be determined. It is also important to work on the literary style of the language in order to expand student's dictionary/vocabulary and fully understand the text you read.

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